

Investigations on bond performances of GFRP reinforcements using distributed fiber optical sensors

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Abstract

In this work, the bond behaviour between concrete and glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars is investigated with distributed fibre optical sensors (DFOSs). With the feature of measuring strain along the bar continuously of DFOS, the strain distributions along GFRP bars in the concrete have been fully measured in the first time. Besides, numerical simulations taking into account the non-linear behaviour of concrete material verified have been carried out to verify the test results. Moreover, a parameter study has been carried out to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the bond performances of GFRP reinforcements.

KEYWORDS: Bond behavior; strain distribution; numerical modelling; development length

Introduction

Reinforced concrete typically consists of both steel rebars and concrete. Concrete is widely used for its high compressive strength and relatively low production cost^(Wang, 1985). However, due to its relatively low tensile strength, concrete may not have sufficient strength to bear bending and tensile loads. Consequently, steel rebars are incorporated to supplement the lack of tensile strength of concrete. Despite its many advantages, the corrosion of steel rebars in salty or extreme environments is a significant drawback. This issue has increasingly led to the exploration and development of alternative reinforcement materials with better resistance to corrosion, such as glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars, which can provide a long-lasting and sustainable solution to this problem^(Nanni, De Luca, & Zadeh, 2014). In recent years, GFRP bars have gained popularity as reinforcement materials due to their high tensile strength and superior resistance to corrosion^(40, 2007). However, the effectiveness of the composite material ultimately depends on the bond behavior between GFRP and concrete^(fib, 2000). Proper bond and bar development length is necessary to effectively transfer tensile stress from the rebars to concrete and fully develop the tensile strength of rebars. While experimental testing is the most accurate method for determining the development length of rebars, it can be a time-consuming and costly process. In contrast, numerical simulations offer a more efficient and cost-effective approach. Through numerical simulations, the behavior of the reinforced concrete can be analyzed under different conditions, and the development length can be determined by analyzing the contact stress between the rebar and concrete. This saves resources and reduces the time required to perform experimental tests.

This research focuses on the bond behavior of GFRP bars, particularly the strain distribution. The study utilizes polyimide distributed fiber reinforced sensors (DFOSs) embedded in epoxy adhesive during bond test. Additionally, a 2D numerical model is created to verify the experimental results. The model examines various parameters such as concrete and bar elastic moduli, as well as friction coefficients, to study their effect on strain distribution. The investigation concludes by testing six different bond lengths to establish the development length of GFRP bars.

Experimental program

Materials

Reinforcement bars

As shown in Figure 1(a), The GFRP bars (Firep Rebar P60-12 VE) are made of glass fibers bound by a vinyl-ester resin, with a grey coating (G-GFRP). The weight ratio of fibers in these bars is 79%. Moreover, the mean surface features and standard deviation (σ) of G-GFRP bar Figure 1(b) were

measured and listed in Table 1. In previous bond tests conducted by the authors, the distributed optical fiber sensors (DFOSs) were applied in bar grooves. However, the groove could yield influence on the mechanical behavior of the bar. The properties of G-GFRP bars with groove and without groove were tested in uniaxial tension test and shown in Table 2. It can be seen that there are decreases of 5% in maximum force and ultimate strength. In comparison, the difference in elastic modulus is limited.

c) Groove dimension

Figure 1: Applied bars

Table 1: Surface features of G-GFRP bar

G-GFRP parameters	Mean	σ
a_m (rib height)	0.91 mm	0.12 mm
c (rib spacing)	9.88 mm	0.16 mm
β (rib inclination)	78.76°	1.63°
d (inner diameter)	13.26 mm	0.14 mm
D (outer diameter)	14.78 mm	0.25 mm

Table 2: The characteristic properties of the G-GFRP bar

Variant	Number	Maximum force (kN)		Ultimate strength (MPa)		Elastic modulus (GPa)	
		Mean	σ	Mean	Σ	Mean	σ
G-GFRP	1	130	0	938	0	46.6	0
G-GFRP with groove	2	123	1.5	888	11	46.2	1.0

Concrete

Normal strength concrete C30/37 was prepared in laboratory. After the curing period of 28 days, the bond tests were conducted. Furthermore, three standard 150 × 300 mm cylinders were tested for the determination of compressive strength according to EN 12390-3^(12390-3, 2019). The composition and mean properties of concrete are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Composition and mean properties of concrete

Property	Value
Sand (< 2 mm)	601 kg/m ³
Aggregate (2 mm – 8 mm)	536 kg/m ³
Aggregate (8 mm – 16 mm)	538 kg/m ³
Cement	380 kg/m ³
Water	228 kg/m ³
Compressive strength	35.9 MPa

Bond test

Figure 2 displays the schematic of bond test specimen. Its dimension is 400 mm × 200 mm × 200 mm. The bottom and horizontal concrete covers are 30 mm. The entire length and bond length of G-GFRP bar are 1280 mm and 300 mm, respectively. Moreover, the steel tube was applied at the loaded end to prevent the mechanical damage from the clamp of loading machine^(Standard, 2011). The steel stirrups were employed to enhance the confinement. Two linear variable displacement transducers (LVDT) were applied to measure the displacements of free end and loaded end, respectively. A polyimide DFOS with epoxy adhesive was applied in the G-GFRP bar groove to measure the strain developments within the embedded section. The tests were carried out displacement-controlled at a loading speed of 0.5 mm/min according to Ref. ^(Alkhrdaji et al., 2004; Canadian Standard Association, 2002). Figure 3 illustrates the process of cutting a groove and embedding the DFOS in the groove.

a) Overview

b) Cross section

c) Test setup

Figure 2: Schematic of bond test

a) Groove cutting

b) DFOS in groove

Figure 3: GFRP bar with DFOS in groove

Numerical modelling

Model description

For the efficiency of calculation, the bond test specimen was simulated as a 2D model and symmetrically simplified (Figure 4). The G-GFRP bar including the arch-shape ribs and concrete were simulated as the identical with the bond specimen. In this model, the displacement perpendicular to the direction of the bar (x-axis) was restrained as well as the rotations of the y and z axes. In addition, the degrees of freedom in concrete were also restrained.

Figure 4: Numerical model and boundary condition

Concrete damage plasticity model

To achieve a more accurate simulation of the material behavior of concrete in finite elements, the material model incorporates the concrete damage plasticity (CDP) model. This model is based on the Drucker-Prager and Mohr-Coulomb yield criteria. It is used to simulate the dual behavior of concrete in both tension and compression.

In the compressive behavior of concrete, the material exhibits ideal elasticity when the compressive stress is less than σ_{c0} . Afterwards, plastic deformation occurs. At a certain compressive strength σ_{cu} , a softening effect occurs which leads to a reduction in the load-carrying capacity of the material. This loss in capacity can be quantified using the damage parameter d_c .

In the tensile behavior of concrete, the stress-strain curve typically exhibits a linear region with an elastic modulus E_0 until it reaches the tensile strength σ_{t0} . At this point, microcracks start to form, which gradually coalesce to create larger macroscopic cracks. This leads to a significant drop in strength, as the cracks act as stress concentrators and reduce the ability of the material to carry loads. This loss in capacity can be quantified using the damage parameter d_t .

Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b) represent the correlation between compression stress and inelastic strain and tension stress and cracking strain, respectively. Moreover, Figure 5(c) and Figure 5(d) display the relationship between damage parameter d_c and inelastic strain and damage parameter d_t and cracking strain, respectively.

Figure 5: Concrete response to uniaxial force

The CDP model requires several parameters to accurately simulate the behavior of concrete under various loading conditions. These include the dilation angle ψ , eccentricity ϵ , the ratio of biaxial to uniaxial compressive yield stresses (σ_b/σ_c), the form factor K_c , and the viscosity parameter μ . Their specific values are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Material parameters in CDP

Dilation angle Ψ	Eccentricity ϵ	σ_b/σ_c	Form factor K_c	Viscosity μ
38°	0.1	1.16	0.667	0.0001

Bar-concrete interface and mesh

In order to understand the bond behavior between rebar and concrete, the contact conditions must correspond closely to the actual implementation. The surface-to-surface method is defined between nodes^(Abaqus, 2011). The tangent behavior of a surface is determined by the friction coefficient, which generates the shear force when the surface begins to slide. The normal behavior, on the other hand, is controlled by the concept of "hard contact." This means that a limited amount of penetration is allowed before contact constraints are activated. Additionally, some transfer of tensile stress is permitted across the interface before contact constraints are deactivated. As shown in Figure 6, the model was meshed into four-node CPE4R elements.

Figure 6: Bar and concrete meshes

Experimental Results and numerical validation

Figure 7(a) displays the relationship between the tensile force and slip of the loaded end. It can be seen that the curves have a sharp increase before 60 kN and 1 mm. Afterwards, the increase became slow. However, no slips were detected at the free ends. Figure 7(b) displays the strain distributions of GFRP bars at four different loads including 25 kN, 50 kN, 75 kN and 100 kN. The free and loaded ends are defined as $x=0$ mm and $x=300$ mm, respectively, as shown in Figure 2(a). Additionally, a length of 50 mm (300 mm to 350 mm), subjected to pure tension, is also analyzed. The DFOSs were partly damaged at the pure tension area under 100 kN. This led to the signal loss of strain measurement. It can be observed that the strain increase from the free end to the loaded end in a nonlinear manner. Moreover, the strain increase with the load. The increase reaches 4000 $\mu\epsilon$ at the loaded end. Then the bar strain kept at a same level within the section under pure tension, which agrees well with the theoretical situation.

(a) Slips of loaded ends

(b) Strain distribution of GFRP bar at different loads

Figure 7: Bond test results

During the experimental program, it is possible that the elastic modulus of concrete and G-GFRP bars from the same batch may vary due to differences in quality. This variation can affect the strain development of the bar and can lead to discrepancies between measured values and simulation results. Figure 8(a) illustrates this comparison between measured values and simulation results, considering three different elastic modulus of concrete, for embedded G-GFRP bars at a tension force of 100 kN. It can be seen that there is no difference on the developed bar strains within the pure tension area. However, this becomes obvious around the loaded end and increase with the less distance to the free end. Furthermore, the higher strain can be obtained with less elastic modulus of concrete. The experimental values show a good agreement with the simulation results obtained with 35.8 GPa of elastic modulus of concrete as the coordinate is less than 200 mm. Afterwards, the difference between measured bar strains and simulation results increase significantly. Figure 8(b) displays the comparison between the experimental results and the simulation results with three different elastic modulus of G-GFRP bars. Different from Figure 8(a), three simulation results have a good agreement around the free end. The difference increase as the coordinate becomes large, and it reach the maximum within the section of pure tension. The test results agrees well with simulation results as the coordinate is less than 200 mm. Then the difference becomes significantly. In addition, the influence of f_r (friction coefficient) on the strain distribution is investigated in Figure 8(c). The trends between all results are much similar to Figure 8(a). It's important to note that the lower friction coefficient lead to higher strain. Figure 8(d) shows the comparison between test results and two simulation results with a fixed elastic modulus of GFRP bar and different friction coefficients. The corresponding result agrees well with the test results as the elastic modulus of GFRP and the friction coefficient reach 40 GPa and 0.5.

a) Elastic modulus of concrete

b) Elastic modulus of G-GFRP bar

c) Friction coefficient

d) Friction coefficient and fixed elastic modulus of G-GFRP bar

Figure 8: Comparison of the strain distributions between the bond test and numerical simulation at 100 kN with different parameters

The determination of development length

The development length is defined as the necessary embedded length to develop the full tensile strength of bar and successfully transfer the bar stress to the concrete (Pay, Canbay, & Frosch, 2014; Standardization, 2004). Moreover, the lap-spliced length is always calculated according to the development length (Canadian Standards Association, 2006; Committee, 1996; Institute, 2015). Therefore, the development length plays a critical role in reinforced concrete structures and needs further analysis.

The embedded length was altered to determine the effective development length of G-GFRP bar. In order to observe the displacement developments of the G-GFRP bar, two reference points at bottom G-GFRP bar (RPg) and bottom concrete (RPc) were marked (Figure 9). Moreover, pulling force (PF) is also taken as a factor to determine the development length.

Figure 9: Reference points of GFRP

As shown in Figure 10, six different types of embedded lengths including 300 mm / 250 mm / 240 mm / 230 mm / 200 mm / 150 mm were applied in numerical simulation. In general, the displacements and pulling force are increasing with the pulling distance as the pulling distance is less than 15 mm. Afterwards, the pulling distances for the variants with embedded lengths greater than 230 mm come to an end, indicating the rupture of G-GFRP bars. In contrast, the pulling distances remain continuous when the embedded length is less than 230 mm, indicating that the development length of G-GFRP bar is 230 mm.

a) Concrete bottom reference point

b) Bar bottom reference point

c) Pulling force

Figure 10: The determination of development length according to different reference points
 Figure 11 shows the contact stress distribution along the embedded length of 230 mm under different loads. The fluctuation of contact stress is directly related to the length and depth of the ribs. The depth of the rib impacts the amplitude of contact stress, while the length affects the wavelength. The contact stress starts to increase at the load end for the curve with 12 kN. As the load reaches 42 kN, the contact stress in the latter section becomes more significant. From 61 kN to the maximum force of 107.81 kN before pullout, contact stresses in each rib gradually increase, except for the rib closest to the free end. The increase in contact stress on the rib closest to the free end leads to a significant rise in tensile stress on the concrete adjacent to the rib, eventually resulting in fracturing. Furthermore, due to the fracture at the bottom of the concrete, the contact stress on the last rib drops rapidly to below average when pulling out the GFRP. Hence, the last rib plays a crucial role during pullout testing in a critical state.

Figure 11: The comparison of contact stress of development length (230 mm) under different pulling force

Conclusions and outlook

In this investigation, the numerical simulation is applied to validate the experimental results in bond test and determine the development length of one type of GFRP bar. The following conclusions can be achieved.

1. The experimental results of bond test can be reproduced in numerical simulation with accurate modeling and material parameters.
2. The concrete properties, such as elastic modulus and friction coefficient, have a significant influence on the strain distribution primarily around the free end of the embedded bar. On the other hand, the different GFRP bar properties have a more significant impact mainly around the loaded end of the embedded bar on the strain distribution.
3. The development length of 230 mm determined in numerical simulation can be applied in design of G-GFRP reinforced concrete structures.

In order to conduct advanced studies, creating a 3D model with accurate rib geometry is crucial. This will enable more accurate comparison with the results obtained in this study.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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